

IN TEACHING INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES REQUIREMENTS

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ANNOTATION

The article highlights the advantages of using the main principles and rules of requirements for the current teaching process in the educational process of general education schools.

Key words: Lesson, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

INTER:Development of the ability of independent creative thinking of the trained personnel is recognized as one of the most important tasks of the educational system. Because, in the conditions of the market economy, only a person who has the ability to think independently can find solutions to his problems and gain his position in society. Of course, this ability is formed first in the family, and later in educational institutions. In this regard, if the lesson is conducted in the form of training using modern interactive methods, and it is logical-structural - organizational (preparation), calling (challenge), understanding (independent learning), reasoning (generalization - strengthening) and homework if it consists of stages (phases), it will be effective.

Organizational stage - formation of small groups, conducting a mental or action game, defining and discussing lesson goals, if necessary, improving them taking into account the suggestions of students and achieving unanimous acceptance, learning new material covers such aspects as the formation of educational motives for learning. In the challenge stage, students' existing information on the new topic is activated in small groups. The student has a strong desire for new knowledge and a self-chosen goal. At this stage, the following 3 goals are implemented:

The first step is to determine what information the student has on the newly studied problem .

The second stage is student activation. In this case, an active activity is carried out, such as to arouse interest in their accelerated, specific goal, to raise previously acquired knowledge to the level of consciousness , to express it to oneself or to a partner in written or oral form.

It is the fourth stage - creating a motive for students to learn a specific subject (educational question) . The goals of the lesson, as well as the goals determined by the students themselves, are more effective than the goals set by the teacher.

A n glash is the second stage of expression, thinking. In it, students encounter

new information (ideas). This information can be presented to students in the form of text, video, oral presentation and performance of experiments. The main task of this stage is to maintain the activities and interests created in the previous process, as well as the aspirations of each student for independent learning.

In addition, it is important that students monitor their own learning. They connect and compare new information (ideas) with their previously formed ideas, that is, new information is connected with activated information in the second stage. Comprehension of the new learning material is the most important task of this stage.

Reflection is the third stage of the lesson. It is at this stage that students consolidate the newly acquired knowledge and express their personal opinions, changing their preconceived notions (if necessary). Also, at this stage, students exchange ideas in a lively way and enrich their vocabulary. As a result, the knowledge acquired in the previous stages is generalized, strengthened, and a different (complete) image of the studied issue is formed and the worldview is increased. Such changes can happen only when the student achieves his learning goal. Thus, the student rises from a lower level of mastery to a higher level. This is reflected in his ability to express new ideas and information in his own words. Students remember better what they like best. The purpose of this stage is to organize dialogue and polylogue between students. Also at this stage it is possible to think and consider several options of the discussion.

The acquired new knowledge is compared with the educational goals, and the level of adherence to them is analyzed. Activities of leading students are encouraged. In short, the reflection phase determines the effectiveness and outcome of the lesson.

Each lesson ends with homework. It should be noted that at each stage of the modern lesson, students' independent thinking, active work in small groups, and the teacher's tasks of advising them, guiding them, and controlling their cognitive activities are ensured. implementation and even the assessment of the activities of the instructors (small groups) should be managed to be transferred to the export team.

In general, in a modern lesson, the teacher should not be the only source of information, but a facilitator, that is, a person who facilitates the independent learning of students and creates favorable conditions for their cognitive activities.

The most basic requirements for the current modern lesson:

I - Didactic requirements

- II - Psychological requirements
- III - Hygienic requirements
- IV – Technological requirements

Based on these requirements, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

1. Clear and positive fulfillment of the DTS requirement.
2. Determining the possibility of the student's level of knowledge, taking into account the age of the students.
3. Targeting based on student interest.
4. Forming the students' level of knowledge based on the program, paying attention to independent thinking, correct and objective assessment of creative works. To encourage his attitude and diligence to knowledge based on creative scores, pay attention to free thinking to improve his memory.
5. Organization of the scientific environment through the rational planning of the lesson.
6. Conveying to children the concepts and events that students should learn in the lesson based on the requirements of the time. Forming a worldview through these , giving importance to interdisciplinary integration.
7. Forming the skills and qualifications of students , directing them to the profession based on the student's ability and the demand of the time.
8. Use of reflective, training, innovative, teaching and positive work demonstration tools in the lesson, organization of problem lessons. Improving students' thinking, teaching them to analyze information and data.
9. Introducing differentiated education and objectively evaluating the level of students' knowledge in the rating system .
10. To teach students analysis, synthesis and efficient use of time.
11. Equipping the classroom based on modern requirements, paying attention to the effective use of scientific and technical progress and the availability of auxiliary tools.
12. Paying attention to the requirements of hygiene and aesthetics and demanding from students.
13. Choosing the right teaching method for the subject, finding clear solutions to problem situations.
14. Plan that they should pay attention to self-analysis in the lesson.

CONCLUSION

Thus, any method requires the purpose of its application, the activities for the implementation of this goal, and the means of performance of the activity. These tools can be objective or intellectual knowledge about the object of activity, necessarily

achieving the set goal. All of these are desirable for any method, but not sufficient for teaching methods.

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